

The Implications of Classroom Testing on English Language Teaching/Learning at Government Degree Colleges in Telangana, India: An Impact Study

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Abstract:

The study proposes to assess the influence of classroom testing and assessment on the teaching and learning of English at the tertiary level at Government Degree Colleges in Telangana, India. Using 33 Government Degree Colleges in Telangana, the study attempts to evaluate the Continuous Internal Evaluation (CIE), and its washback on the teaching and learning of English. The profile of the learners of the college mirrors in microcosm the undergraduate learner profile of the 135 Government Degree Colleges (GDCs) in the 33 districts in Telangana to include rural, semi-rural, semi-urban, and urban undergraduate learners. The study period is four years from 2016- 2017 to 2019- 2020, i.e., the four semesters of the General English Course of undergraduate study. Internal Assessment Question Papers and Assignments were reviewed, and teachers and students from 33 Government Degree Colleges were included in this study to represent the 135 GDCs in the 33 Districts of Telangana, India. Using Bloom's learning taxonomy as a theoretical framework, items in the CIE is analyzed to determine the cognitive complexities required by the students to respond to the test items. The study highlights the patterns in which the high and low order learning are prioritized in the classroom assessments. The findings reveal a strong relationship between classroom assessment, teaching practices and students' learning of English and washback is a predominant phenomenon in teaching /learning English at the tertiary level in GDCs in Telangana.

1. Introduction

The present study proposes to examine the impact of classroom assessment on English language teaching and learning at the tertiary level in Telangana by studying assessment practices, its issues, and implications at 33 select Government Degree Colleges to represent the 135 GDCs in the 33 Districts of Telangana, India. The three crucial aspects in language testing and assessment represent the significant developments in the field over the past 50 are test validation, washback research, and research into teachers' classroom assessment practices. The present study examines these three vital aspects of testing and assessment in teaching, learning, and testing English at the tertiary level in Telangana by studies conducted at select Government Degree Colleges. The study used 33 Government Degree Colleges, one from each district of Telangana as representative colleges of the 135 Government Degree Colleges to include the rural, semi-rural, semi-urban and urban undergraduate learner profiles. The surveys have suggested that undergraduate learners in GDCs across Telangana belong to the socio-economically challenged sections of the

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society, often first-generation learners and the thrust area of General English Curriculum across the GDCS is on developing the Language skills of the learners. The study observed the effect of classroom assessment on the teaching-learning process and examined if washback can be 'predicted' or 'controlled' in teaching-learning contexts.

Teachers and students helped determine how classroom assessment practices influence the teaching and learning process in Government Degree Colleges and the relationship between assessment and teaching practices and students' learning of English and the feedback collected through the questionnaires administered has reflected the positive and /or negative impact of assessments on the teaching and learning of English to gauge if the washback of assessments is a predominant phenomenon in teaching and learning English at Government Degree Colleges in Telangana State.

2. Rationale/Need for the study

Classroom Assessment and their effect on English language teaching/learning have gained attention in developed countries, mainly because of the continuous research evaluation of their relevance and efficacy. In India, however, not much systematic analysis is found to determine the effects of classroom assessment on teaching and learning English. This study attempts to fill this gap by attempting a comprehensive study to understand how washback can be used to change approaches to teaching and learning and what should be done to enable the impact of washback to be beneficial rather than harmful in Government Degree Colleges in Telangana State.

3. Hypothesis

Assessments are tools to measure the learner's knowledge, skills, and abilities in the English language.

- How and to what extent can tests influence the teaching-learning process of English?
- Can the impact of testing, whether positive or negative, on teaching /learning be predicted or controlled?
- If so, it is essential for language teachers to be competent in language testing and to be able to select appropriate languages tests for their learners to enhance the language learning process.
- If washback is inevitable, teachers should try to enable washback to be beneficial rather than harmful to English language teaching and learning.

4. Objective of Study

Using 33 select Government Degree Colleges in Telangana, the study seeks to determine:

- What does washback look like within the teaching and learning context of Government Degree Colleges in Telangana.?
- Why language teachers need to be competent in language testing and the need for language teachers to select appropriate language tests and the need for language teachers to design and develop appropriate language tests keeping in mind the purpose, context, and the group of test-takers.
- Examine the impact of classroom assessment practices on the teaching /learning process of English at Government Degree Colleges in Telangana.

5. Methodology

The study reviewed the Continuous Internal Evaluation(CIE)/Classroom Assessment of the Colleges and using a desk review approach. It helped understand the issues and implications of the effect of Classroom Assessment on teaching/learning at the undergraduate level in Telangana and identify essential information, trends, issues, and gaps by analyzing available data. It also led to the preparation and aligning of questionnaires and interview questions to gauge perceptions and attitudes of teachers, students about the role of these assessment in the teaching-learning process as it enables validating the information, filling in gaps, and answering key questions ,the washback of classroom assessment on the teaching-learning process and to understand to see if the washback of testing can be 'predicted' or 'controlled' on the teaching-learning process.

6. Approach

The research project adopted a Mixed Method (Quantitative and qualitative) Approach. The research method intends to collect and analyze quantitative (closed-ended) and qualitative (open-ended) data. Inputs from language teachers and a cross-section of undergraduate students from rural, semi-urban and urban areas will help document the nature of examination Impact on teaching and learning of English and examine how washback works on specific areas like the content of teaching, teaching methodology, learning approaches, the attitude of teachers and learners and the extent of presumed impact-positive or negative. The study used material analysis (Question Papers of CIE and, textbooks), questionnaires, interviews, classroom

observation to gather information and document the impact of testing on teaching and learning English at GDCs in Telangana.

7. The Impact Study

The Study focused on Washback -The Impact of Language Testing on English Teaching and Learning. Testing is a crucial feature of teaching and learning. Testing, teaching, and learning can support and hinder each other. Madaus (1988, p.83) states, testing influences "what is taught, how it is taught, what is learned, and how it is learned, rather than the official stated curriculum." Washback" is defined by Alderson and Wall (1993) as the" impact of testing on teaching and learning." Washback has two characteristics: it can positively affect teaching/learning and ensure and promote the achievement of teaching/learning objectives, or it can harm teaching/learning, influence, or even hinder the accomplishment of teaching/learning objectives. Washback is test impact, according to Bachman and Palmer (1996, p.30). It demonstrates its effect at the micro-level, which is its impact on individuals, and at the macro level, its impact on the educational system or society. Hughes(1989) calls washback is "the effect of language testing on teaching and learning," he emphasizes that it can have "positive and negative" influences on the teaching and learning process. Analyzing the washback studies helped to build the foundation for the present research that seeks to study the impact of testing on the teaching and learning in select Government Degree Colleges at the tertiary level in Telangana, India. The study also focuses on Bloom's Taxonomy which is used as a theoretical framework to analyze classroom assessments for test validation in the present study.

The study uses 33 Government Degree Colleges to evaluate the Continuous Internal Evaluation (CIE) for test validation and its washback on teaching and learning of English in these colleges since the introduction of CBCS Telangana in 2016- 2017. The study period is four years from 2016- 2017 to 2019- 2020, i.e., the four semesters of General English Course of 2016-2017 to 2018-2019, 2017- 2018 to 2019-2020 and 2018 -2019 to 2020-2021 batch of undergraduate study.

The study analyzed the Internal Assessments (CIE) Question Papers, which is mandatory in semesters 1, 2, 3 and 4 of the six semesters undergraduate study across courses for a period of four years (2016- 2017 to 2019-2020) to (1) analyze items for its cognitive complexity using Blooms Taxonomy, (2) determine the repetition trend of items in the four years, and (3)

determine Lessons of prescribed General English Textbook from which these items are selected. The study plans to establish the washback effect, the influence of Continuous Internal Evaluation (CIE), to demonstrate if and how testing impacts the teaching/learning of English in Government Degree Colleges in Telangana.

A total of 792 internal Assessment Question Papers, 396 Assignments, were reviewed for test validation and its potential washback on teaching and learning English. The test papers use a variety of methods to test students' competency in English, like multiple-choice questions (MCQs), Gap fills, constructed response questions (CRQs), and extended response questions (ERQs) which were analyzed. Each test item was given three classifications. The first classification determines the cognitive complexities required by the students in responding to the test item according to **Bloom's Taxonomy**. The second classification determines the frequency with which the test items were repeated in the respective semester. The third classification defines the lesson from which the item was selected.

The Table below shows the Scheme of Analysis for CIE /Classroom Assessment

Scheme for Analysis of CIE/Classroom Assessment Batch I (2016-17 to 2018-19), Batch II (2017-18 to 2019-20), Batch 11I(2018-19 to 2020-21)				
Note: General English is a 5 Credit mandatory course in Semesters I, II, III, IV of the 6 Semesters of Undergraduate Programs inTelangana State since the introduction of CBCS in 2016-17.				
Year	Semester I	Semester II	Semester III	Semester IV
2016-2017	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1		
2017-2018	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1
2018-2019	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1
2019-2020			IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1	IQP-2 Asgmt-1 ESQP-1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal Question Papers (IQP) -24 per College (2 IQPs per semester), (24x33 =792) • Assignments (Asgmt)=1 per semester = 12(12X33=396) 				

The study also focuses on understanding the teaching practice and students' learning approaches in the Government Degree Colleges in Telangana. English teachers students of different genders and socio-economic backgrounds were part of the study. The students belong to the 2016-2017 to 2018 to 2019, 2017- 2018 to 2019-2020 and 2018 -2019 to 2020-2021 batch of undergraduate study. Semi-structured interviews and questionnaires on assessment practices were used as the primary tool for data collection from teachers and students. Inputs from language teachers and a cross-section of undergraduate students helped document the nature of test impact on teaching and learning English and examined how washback works on specific areas like the content of teaching, teaching methodology, ways of assessing achievement, the attitude of teachers and learners and the extent of presumed impact – positive or negative.

The study was conducted at 33 ESL classrooms in Government Degree College, to examine the influence of washback of classroom assessment on the teaching /learning process to see if washback can be 'predicted' or 'controlled' in a teaching/learning environment. Classroom observation and analysis of classroom assessment practices of the 33 ESL classrooms helped understand the washback of testing on the teaching-learning process in the English classrooms. Most researchers believe that using better classroom assessment techniques will help students learn and teach better (Cheng & Curtis, 2004). Implementing any test is expected to always result in washback; however, "a single and uniform reaction to each teacher or student is impossible." (Burrows, 2004, p. 125).

The idea is that testing results in positive change or ensures desirable change, but testing often does not achieve what the test designers expected. Alderson (2004,p.xi) states that test developers can only do so much and that teachers' motivations and students' attitudes must be given more consideration. Watanabe (2004, p.19) describes one of the field's most important discoveries: "washback is a highly intricate process, not a monolithic one."

The study reveals if and how Washback is a predominant phenomenon in the teaching and learning English in classrooms at the tertiary level in Government Degree Colleges in Telangana and if the impact of washback can be 'controlled' to be beneficial rather than harmful to the English language teaching and learning at the tertiary level in Telangana.

9. Conclusion

The present study examines the three vital aspects of testing and assessment, namely test validation, washback, and classroom assessment practices. The findings reveal that the tests

are valid and reliable to a large extent. The washback of the CIE and classroom assessment practices are beneficial to the teaching and learning English at 33 select Government Degree Colleges in Telangana and thereby in the 135 Government Degree Colleges across Telangana. undergraduate level Government Degree Colleges in Telangana.

The findings of the research study include:

- Washback is a predominant phenomenon in teaching and learning English at the tertiary level in Government Degree Colleges in Telangana and is mainly positive.
- Alignment of teaching, learning, and testing objectives and outcomes, teacher intervention, attitude, student motivation, well-designed textbooks, well-designed tests assessing the various learning levels of learners, accountability are factors that contribute to positive washback.
- Washback of assessments dominates the teaching/learning process; hence assessments should be trustworthy (i.e., valid and reliable)
- The methods of assessing the students' performance should be clear to the teacher and student.
 - Teachers and students believe that the assessments of students' performance are constructive despite the same assessment procedure being used to evaluate all the students in mixed ability classes.
 - Teachers realize that student assessment should be a continuous activity and know that various assessment techniques can evaluate the students' progress in language learning.
 - The study reveals that students find classroom assessments the CIE scaffolds and helps them in the language learning process by monitoring their progress, retaining language content and skills, and reducing test anxiety.
 - Teachers feel the need for an orientation course in assessment practices as they realize its importance in acquiring language skills, primarily when the same assessment procedure is used to evaluate all the students with mixed language abilities.
 - The survey of undergraduate teachers of English reveals that since they are the actual classroom practitioners, practicing teachers should be involved develop material, design curriculum, and evolve assessments for their students.
 - The study recommends Assessment Literacy as a crucial aspect of faculty development programs in GDCs across Telangana for effective teaching/learning of English

- The study establishes that the impact of washback can be 'controlled' to be beneficial rather than harmful on English language teaching and learning at the tertiary level in Telangana.

Assessment practices are currently undergoing a significant paradigm shift in many parts of the world. Policymakers are aware of the power of assessment and can use them to reform the educational system, introduce new curriculum, textbooks, and new teaching methods. This impact study of testing on English language teaching/ learning is hoped can initiate a trend toward using assessment to improve English language teaching, learning, and testing at the tertiary level in Telangana State.

9. Limitation of the Study

An area of limitation of the study was its inability to include autonomous Government Degree Colleges from various districts in Telangana.

10. Scope for Future Research

The trend in washback studies is changing progressively from investigating if it exists towards determining "what does washback look like? What brings washback about? Why does washback exist?" (Alderson 2004, p.ix). The thrust of washback research has evolved and must continue to shift away from cause-effect relationships between assessments and teaching-learning and towards a better understanding of the complex nature of washback.

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